

Hidden Eye Movements as a Feature of the Biomechanism of Visual Accommodation

Abstract

The article challenges the traditional Helmholtz theory of accommodation, proposing instead a comprehensive cybernetic model. The author argues that visual accommodation is a multi-link, adaptive control system functioning through self-adjusting extremal algorithms. Key concepts include the differentiation between image contrast control (focusing via external eye muscles) and peripheral light flux suppression (collimation via the lens). The research suggests that hidden eye movements (tremor) not only serve as search signals for maximum contrast but also facilitate aqueous humor outflow, linking accommodation dysfunction to age-related pathologies like glaucoma and cataracts.

The problem of understanding and adequately explaining visual accommodation cannot be considered completely solved today. H. Helmholtz's theory of accommodation, by and large, is useful only for the theoretical justification of prescribing eyeglasses and is useless in the prevention and treatment of most diseases of the visual system.

The reason, as it seems, lies in the fact that the fundamental feature of the accommodation process is its automatic nature, and it should be considered primarily on the basis of a cybernetic model, while involving all the subtleties of model representations of ophthalmology itself. An attempt to create such a cybernetic model has already been made previously **(1)** in the form of the simplest model of automatic regulation, according to the regularities of which processes in biosystems do not proceed.

Your attention is invited to some aspects of the cybernetic model of the accommodation control system, which in terms of control theory should be called a "multivariable, adaptive control system, each control loop of which functions according to the algorithm of a self-tuning extremal control system with a search disturbing influence". It was created in the process of many years of research and experiments, the purpose of which was to eliminate the problems of the visual system caused by presbyopia **(2)**. The research method consisted in the analysis of available theoretical material (in ophthalmology), its critical comprehension, and the creation on this basis of a hypothetical control model that eliminates existing paradoxes and contradictions. The visual sensations and the target result achieved as a result of training served as an evaluation of the adequacy of the model.

A feature of the accommodation control system, in our opinion, is that it simultaneously controls and manages several interdependent processes, such as managing the contrast of the image in the fovea region (image focusing), and cutting off the light flux from the periphery of the fields of vision of each eye, which could fall on the fovea region. Focusing is provided by a change in the shape of the eye by the external muscles of the eye, and the cutting off of the peripheral light flux by a change in the curvature and orientation of the lens.

The speed of the process of managing the contrast of object contours and interference differs: for contrast, it is of the order of hundreds of hertz of ocular tremor; for suppressing

the peripheral flux of light on the fovea, it is fractions of a hertz (by the method of controlling the curvature and orientation of the lens); for narrowing the pupil diameter, it is even less. The most important feature of the accommodation control system is that for managing these processes, periodic changes in the shape of the eye (tremor of the eye muscles) occur in it, caused by the external muscles of the eyeball. These changes in the shape of the eye cause micro-changes in ocular pressure and, as a consequence, changes in the curvature of the cornea and focusing (contrast of contours on the retina). Based on this change, the control algorithm of the control system (the brain) determines how the muscles need to act in order to achieve maximum contrast at the fovea. The change in the curvature and orientation of the lens and pupil diameter occurs according to a similar scenario, only the mechanical drive of this process is the ciliary muscle.

It is highly probable that the process of cutting off the interfering fluxes of light from the periphery of the fields of vision of each eye proceeds as follows:

1. At the initial stage of adjustment, the ciliary muscles of both eyes relax, the fields of vision diverge horizontally for their separate perception and the corresponding optimal adjustment for each eye individually.
2. Further, the fields of vision combine into one, and a process of periodic switching of the alignment of the fields of vision on one of them occurs, thereby ensuring binocularity of vision and visual acuity for each eye individually.

It is thanks to such auxiliary search movements (disturbing influences) that it becomes possible to maintain the optimal quality of visual perception. The slowest control process is carried out by changing the pupil diameter. It also serves the purpose of suppressing the peripheral light flux on the fovea and is auxiliary to the process of controlling the orientation and curvature of the lens **(6)**.

Search disturbing movements with age can go beyond permissible limits and cause disruption of the functioning of the visual system. As it appears, search disturbing movements are innate and, in addition to the accommodation process, ensure the outflow of aqueous humor along the uveoscleral and trabecular outflow pathways **(3, 4)**. During sleep, in the phase of paradoxical (REM) sleep, it is the renewing search disturbing movements that provide an increase in the outflow of aqueous humor, reducing intraocular pressure. Disruptions of search disturbing movements with age can lead to such age-related pathologies as cataracts, retinal degeneration, and glaucoma.

It should be particularly emphasized that H. Helmholtz's idea that changing the curvature of the lens serves the purpose of focusing the image on the retina is wrong in principle, for the visual stimulus for the contraction of the ciliary muscle is not the lack of sharpness of the image on the retina. In reality, in our opinion, the change in the curvature and orientation of the lens aims at maximum limitation of the interfering light flux from the periphery of the fields of vision to the fovea region (something similar to physical collimation). That is, the change in the curvature of the lens during near vision minimizes the light flux falling on the retinal area around and inside the fovea.

To realize this, it is probably necessary to consider the conditions of functioning of the visual system at the early stages of its evolution. These were a light background, and against this light background, it was necessary to distinguish the contours of opaque objects, the nature of their movement, and the distance to them. All this is necessary for

displaying the environment, its modeling by consciousness, and survival. At an early stage of the evolution of the visual system, this task was solved by focusing the contours of the image of opaque objects on the retina of the eye by changing the shape of the eyeball with the external muscles of the eyeball and, presumably, by analyzing their diffraction pattern. This initially embedded process of focusing the contours of opaque objects by changing the shape of the eyeball was the foundation for the development and improvement of the visual system in the process of evolution. Its imperfection lies in the following: a small focusing range in terms of distance, the possibility of brightness inversion inside the image contour, and a change in the shape of the image on the retina itself – everything inherent in Fresnel diffraction.

After the appearance of warm-blooded animals, according to our assumptions, the relative constancy of body temperature provided an additional possibility of focusing by changing the curvature of the lens. The implementation of such a method of improving image clarity in warm-blooded animals is justified by the following factors: due to changes in the body temperature of cold-blooded animals, a powerful intraocular muscle is required to change the shape of the lens at low temperatures. For warm-blooded animals, whose temperature is constant and higher than the ambient temperature, there is no need for a powerful intraocular muscle to control the shape of the lens due to the greater elasticity of the lens at a constant and higher body temperature. But, in fact, evolutionary transformations associated with changes in the shape of the lens and its orientation, in the process of evolution, began to be carried out in another, most optimal way from the point of view of the quality of visual perception. However, in our view, a fundamentally new way of adapting the visual system to different distances arose in the process of evolution: focusing the contour of the image of an opaque object in the fovea region under the minimum light flux in the fovea region from the peripheral region of vision. The focusing of the contour itself, as before, is carried out by changing the shape of the eyeball, but already in conditions of the maximum achievable parallelism of the light flux on the fovea, along with the narrowing of the pupil. This causes minimal requirements for the range of change in the shape of the eyeball **(5, 6)**.

The stated regularities so far represent only a plausible hypothesis, but the presented hypothesis opens up a new sector of search for understanding and explaining the biomechanisms of accommodation.

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Note: This article was translated from Russian. The author does not speak English fluently and may not be able to respond to comments or participate in discussions in English